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Report

CROATIA

Migration and demographic patterns in Central-Eastern Europe

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Report

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Abstract

This report is a part of deliverable “D.6.2. Report on migration and demographic patterns in the EU CEE countries and potential source countries” from the project FUME – Future Migration Scenarios for Europe (870649), financed with the Horizon 2020 programme. In particular, this country report focuses on critical analysis of migration data from Croatia, and in particular - immigration data. The analysis consists of an overview of stock and flow data on migrants including such dimensions as age groups, gender and the country of origin. This report is a first step in analytical task which aims to determine migration potential from and to Croatia and, furthermore, to provide necessary data input for fine-tuning of FUME migration projection model.

The Republic of Croatia is located in southeastern Europe on the Balkan Peninsula. It has joined the European Union in 2013, but it is not a member of the Schengen Area yet. Croatia has been facing significant challenges due to the aging processes and depopulation – due to negative demographic processes (such as low birth rate) and extensive emigration of the working age population.

Historically, Croatia was characterized by high emigration to overseas destinations, such as America and Australia, and to Western Europe. Since independence from Yugoslavia in 1991, emigration has continued while immigration processes were very significant (with the notable exception of refugees from other Balkan states). After joining the EU in 2013, Croatia has experienced a further demographic decline due to emigration of mostly younger generations to other European countries with a higher level of socioeconomic development. It includes the emigration of highly skilled professionals, which is a relatively new feature in Croatian migration history. These processes account for negative migration balance characteristic of Croatia’s recent history.

Immigration trends, however, are expected to change since the EU membership and recent economic growth make Croatia more attractive for foreign workers. Membership in the Schengen Area, which is planned for the nearest future, can also impact immigration level. For the moment, however, Croatia has one of the lowest immigrant/inhabitant ratio among EU member states. While in 2019 the majority of EU member states observed more immigrants than emigrants, Croatia was one of a few exceptions (Eurostat, 2021).

1. Introduction

The Republic of Croatia is located in southeast Europe on the Balkan Peninsula. It has a population of 3,9 million inhabitants (as of January 2022) (Croatian Bureau of Statistics [CBS], 2022, Census). For centuries, it experienced political turbulences and occupations by various powers, such as Venetia, the Ottoman Empire, and the Austro-Hungarians, which impacted ethnic composition, multicultural exchanges, and historical migration processes. In the 20th century, Croatia was mainly an emigration country. Until the World War II, economy was the key motive for leaving the country, especially from the rural areas which were affected by crises and overpopulation. Both Americas, and later also Australia, New Zealand and other countries, attracted poor, unskilled migrants offering them jobs in factories, mines and other sectors. Following the war, political emigration appeared, while economic one continued (Gregurović, Mlinarić, 2012; Koprić, Novak, Giljević, 2021). During the second part of the 20th century, Croatia was part of the Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia, and in 1991 declared independence. Emigration, however, continued and even increased in the 1990s, since at that time, for five years Croatia was involved in the War of Independence. As a result, thousands of Croats were displaced throughout the former Yugoslavia or emigrated outside of the Balkans. Also, non ethnic Croats, mostly Serbs, left Croatia following the outbreak of the war (Winland, 2020). According to the census data from 2011, since 1991 there has been a decrease of 420,000 people who were not ethnic Croats (Koprić, Novak, Giljević, 2021: 216).

Croatia became the member of the Council of Europe in 1996 and of the European Union in 2013. It signed the Schengen Treaty in 1995, but it still has not been admitted to the Schengen Area due to several reasons, one of them being the challenges of border control as Croatia's borders will become Schengen's external borders. Croatian policy-makers expect their country to join the border-free area in the second half of 2024, however the European Commission has not declared any specific date (ETIAS, 2021).

In the last decade, admission to the EU has had a significant impact on Croatia's demography and migration patterns. On the one hand, it has experienced a further demographic decline due to the emigration of mostly younger generations to other European countries with a higher level of socio-economic development. Since 2015 the migration flows doubled, because of the full freedom of movement that Croatian citizens gained across most of the EU region. On the other hand, the EU membership raised the country's attractiveness for prospective immigrants, and thus immigration is expected to increase in the nearest future. This shift has already begun, and Croatia is currently resembling the patterns in other new EU member states, such as Poland, Czech Republic, Hungary, Slovakia, Romania or Slovenia, which witness a significant influx of immigrant workers who take advantage of the region's economic development, political stability, and job opportunities (Brzozowski, Banović, Alpeza, 2021). It was also predicted that after the accession to the EU, Croatia would attract not only economic legal migrants, but also transit and illegal workers (Gregurović, Mlinarić 2012; Knezović, Grošinić, 2017).

Croatia resembles to some extent the migration patterns observed in Central and Eastern Europe. As indicated above, historically it had a predominantly emigration profile and thus there were no particular policies designed for immigrants and their integration. The exception are refugees and asylum seekers. Since 1990s, Croatia has hosted, among others, around 400,000 of refugees from Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo and Macedonia (Koprić, Novak, Giljević, 2021: 216).

Regarding the ethnic composition, apart from Croats who constitute 89,6% of the country's inhabitants, the most numerous is the Serbian minority (4,4%). Other minorities constitute less than 1% of the population: Bosnians (0,5%), Italians (0,45%), Hungarians (0,37%), Albanians (0,34%), Slovenes (0,3%) and other smaller groups (Migrants and Refugees, 2020).

Preliminary results from the census conducted in 2021 reveal a drastic fall in the population in comparison to 2011 which had not been expected by the policy-makers. It seems that the country has lost about 10 percent of its inhabitants during the last decade, from 4,3 million to 3,9 million people. The decrease affected many regions, including the capital city of Zagreb (CBS, 2022, Census). According to the demographic statistics, the last time Croatia had so little inhabitants was in 1948 (Grgurinovic, 2022).

Picture: Spencer Davis/Unsplash

2. Methodology, Definition and Sources

Methodological approach

This report is based upon a desk research method and critical data analysis. Firstly, we have gathered the main relevant empirical data on immigration statistics (stock and flows) from official sources in Croatia and other Central, Eastern and Southern European countries belonging to the EU. Data were obtained from state sources, including the Croatian Bureau of Statistics, Eurostat, reports and surveys on recent migration processes related to the analysed country. Relevant academic literature and policy papers have also been reviewed. The main theme of interest was immigration, but a short overview of historical trends, emigration processes and diaspora are also included. The research team has paid special attention to existing, current data on immigrant stocks and flows. The report provides a critical assessment of those data and their characteristics, suggesting biases and problems in data collection and reliability. The migration statistics provided by the official Croatian sources was finally compared with the estimations on immigrant flows by Abel & Cohen (2019).

Evidencing of migrants in statistical registers and definitions of migrants

Data on migration are collected by the Ministry of Interior and published on the CBS website. In 2011, to comply with the international standards, the Croatian state authorities adopted a new methodology for evidencing international migration movements. It included relevant UN recommendations and EU regulations. Since then, the definition of international migrant has related to the concept of usual residence (CBS, 2022a), which is defined by the EU as the "place at which a person normally spends the daily period of rest, regardless of temporary absences (...) or the place of legal or registered residence" (European Commission, 2022). To be counted as an international migrant, a person needs to change their country of usual residence for at least one year.

The major change in statistical registers refers also to the temporary migrants:

According to the methodology that was used until 2010, the international migration statistics included the citizens of the Republic of Croatia and foreigners with the granted permanent stay in the Republic of Croatia who registered or cancelled their place of permanent residence in the Republic of Croatia (CBS, 2022a).

Since 2011, apart from people granted permanent stay also those with a temporary one have been included in the official immigration records. Earlier, only migrants granted permanent stay were recorded.

Currently, Croatian statistics on international migrants are based upon the following definitions:

A migrant - a person who changed a place of residence (immigrant, emigrant) for at least one year.

International migration of population - the change of a country of usual residence.

The *international migration statistics* refer to data on international migration flows, i.e., "the data on number and characteristics of persons who changed their country of usual residence in a given calendar year" (Ibidem).

Foreigner, (according to the Foreigners Act), is “any person who is not a Croatian national, but has the nationality of one of the Member States of the European Economic Area (EEA), the Swiss Confederation, the nationality of third-country or is a stateless person” (CBS, 2021a).

Third-country national is foreigner who is not national of the EEA Member States or the Swiss Confederation (Ibidem).

According to the Foreigners Act, temporary residence may be granted to people for one of the following purposes: family reunification, education, research, humanitarian reasons, life partnership, work, work of posted workers. Besides, permanent stay can be granted to third-country national who had been residing in Croatia for at least five consecutive years (Ibidem).

Those kind of migration data are collected regularly and published by the CBS.

It is important to note that data on emigration gathered by the Croatian Bureau of Statistics are based on the self-reporting by migrants themselves. It leads to a serious underestimation of emigration size. One of the problems is the lack of specific deadlines for temporary migrants to report their movement as well as the legal ambiguity in this field which rather discourage people from reporting (cf. Ivanović, 2019).

Moreover, a vital reason may be the willingness to keep health and other social benefits to which Croatian citizens may be eligible (Pavić and Ivanović, 2019).

Another important concept that should be discussed here is the “Croatian diaspora” used by the state. It is defined as a group which consists of “Croatian emigrants and their descendants who live overseas and in European countries.” In order to estimate its size, the state officials collect available information from a variety of sources, including: the data collected by Croatian diplomatic missions and consular offices, Croatian Roman Catholic missions, census findings from the countries where emigrants currently reside. Additionally, some estimates of the Croatian diaspora communities are made, but the methodology is not specified (Government of the Republic of Croatia, 2022).

Methodologically, estimating the number of Croatian emigrants constitutes a huge challenge. In existing analyses there are various approaches to defining a “Croatian emigrant.” Some migration research include in that category all people who left Croatia, while other studies count solely ethnic Croats. There are also analyses which add descendants of emigrants to the whole “emigration stock.” It is, therefore, impossible to have a consistent view of these figures (Škvorc, 2005, as cited in Gregurović, Mlinarić, 2012: 112).

Picture: Kellie Benz/Unsplash

There is a discrepancy between the attention paid by the media and policy-makers to refugee and irregular migration as opposed to other migrant flows.

3. Croatian Diaspora

Emigration of Croatian citizens and the Croatian diaspora constitute complex political topics. It is, among others, the legacy of former Yugoslavia and ethno-national tensions between communities. The independent Croatian nation-state has a vivid interest in keeping ties with its large diaspora. For that reason, it provides various incentives and tools for Croat minorities living in the Balkan states as well as in other European and overseas regions (Mlinarić 2008, Winland 2020).

According to the Croatian authorities, the number of Croatians and their descendants who live outside of their home country is around 3,200,000 (Government of the Republic of Croatia, 2022), which is not far from the size of current population of Croatia (approximately 3,9 million in 2022). From a historical perspective, there were several periods of Croatian emigration, and the popular destinations were as follows (Government of the Republic of Croatia, 2022a):

- **the 1880s** - First World War: United States, Latin America, South Africa, Australia, New Zealand
- **1918 - World War II**: Germany, France, Belgium
- **After World War II**: Latin America and North America
- **After 1965**: Western Europe, Australia, New Zealand and Canada - mostly economic migration
- **After the 1990s**: Germany, Switzerland, Austria, Canada, USA, Australia and New Zealand

The top ten countries with the largest Croatian diaspora, according to Croatian authorities, are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The countries with the most numerous Croatian diaspora

Source: Government of the Republic of Croatia, 2022a

Country	The size of Croatian diaspora (approximate estimates)
US	1,200,000
Germany	500,000
Argentina	250,000
Australia	250,000
Canada	250,000
Chile	200,000
New Zealand	100,000
Austria	90,000
Switzerland	80,000
Brazil	70,000

According to other sources, important countries hosting Croatians are the states that had been part of the Yugoslavia, in particular: Bosnia and Herzegovina (where Croats constitute one of the main nationalities), Serbia and Slovenia. Although other countries appear in various documents, the numbers regarding Croatian population differ (cf. Winland 2020:93).

Additionally, apart from political issues, methodological challenges, described in the previous section, make the task of precise estimation of the diaspora size almost impossible.

The UE membership in 2013, and particularly the free movement granted to Croatia in 2015 has led to a major increase in the number of emigrants, resulting in further population decline. According to the Croatian Bureau of Statistics in 2020 the number of people who emigrated from Croatia was 34.043, which constituted a slight decline in comparison to the period of 2016 – 2019. In 2012, before joining European Union, the number was 12,877. In 2020, out of the total number of emigrants, the majority, i.e., 61,4% were Croatian citizens, while 36,8% - foreigners. Another feature of emigration from Croatia is masculinization – 64,4% of emigrants were men (CBS 2021a).

Figure 1. International migration flows: Emigration, 2012-2020.

Source: CBS, 2021.

The most popular current destinations for Croatian citizens are Germany, Ireland and Austria. The major motivations for emigration are as follows: the lack of jobs, labour and career opportunities, limited entrepreneurial options and a perception of higher quality of life in Western Europe (European Commission, 2021; cf. Knezović, Grošinić, 2017: 10). From a demographic perspective, the key issue is the working age of most Croatian migrants, which is a huge challenge for the Croatian economy and the state in general (Winland 2020).

4. Immigrant stock in Croatia

As in the case of emigration, since Croatia joined the EU in 2013 and became entitled to the free movement regime in 2015 across almost all of the EU area, immigration has been increasing. Thus, it has become an 'new-old' immigration state, like many other parts of the post-communist Europe (Brzozowski, Banović, Alpeza, 2021: 4).

Even though the very first Census 2021 results were already published, they refer only to the population as a whole, to households and housing units (CBS, 2022), and no detailed results were issued until the point of writing this report.

For now (January 2022), Census 2011 results remain the main comprehensive source of data concerning immigrant stock in Croatia.

According to the data from 2011 presented by Croatian Bureau of Statistics, there were 22 527 foreign citizenship holders living in the country and constituted 0,53% of the whole population (CBS, 2013).

Figure 2. International migration flows: Emigration, 2012-2020.
Source: CBS, 2013a.

The most numerous immigrant group (6 733 persons) living in Croatia in 2011 originated from Bosnia and Herzegovina. Almost 30% of the whole immigrant population had Bosnian citizenship. The second largest group consisted of Serbians - there were almost 3 thousand citizens of this country in Croatia in 2011 and they constituted a 12,8% share of all the foreigners. Other relatively large groups of foreign immigrants living in Croatia in 2011 consisted of people originating from Slovenia (1 999 persons), Germany (1 609), Italy (1 420), Kosovo (1 188) and Macedonia (1 034).

Analysing the population data by concerning country of birth, a completely different scale of immigrant stock appears. The number of foreign-born inhabitants of Croatia amounted to 584 947 in 2011 with major countries of birth being Bosnia and Herzegovina (409 357 persons), Serbia (52 763), Germany (34 148), Kosovo (20 347), Slovenia (19 803) and Macedonia (10 167). The most feminized among these groups was the one consisting of people born in Slovenia and the least feminized one – in Kosovo.

Figure 3. Most numerous immigrant groups with feminization rates, by country of birth, 2011.

Source: CBS, 2013c.

Some statistical data concerning Census 2011 that are available in the CBS database refer to all the people who immigrated to their place of residence until the Census 2011, meaning that they include Croatian return migrants as well. It is more of a footage of numbers of people who ever immigrated to Croatia than a number of foreigners residing in the country in a specific point of time. Nevertheless, it is the only source of information about the sex structure of the immigrant population in 2011 and it shows that the feminization rate among all the groups was around 50% with the largest share of women in a group consisting of people who immigrated to Croatia from Serbia.

Table 2. Most numerous groups of people who immigrated from abroad, by sex, with feminization rates indicated, 2011.

Source: CBS, 2013b.

	All	Bosnia and Herzegovina	Germany	Serbia	Slovenia	Kosovo	Other countries
All	604 902	271 211	120 717	73 112	25 844	14 917	99 101
Men	293 029	125 347	63 868	33 038	12 000	7 811	50 965
Women	311 873	145 864	56 868	40 074	13 844	7 106	48 136
% of women	51,56%	53,78%	47,09%	54,81%	53,57%	47,64%	48,57%

Croatian Bureau of Statistics does not share any other type of statistical information about immigrant stock in their public database. However, some more updated information is provided by Eurostat, indicating general immigrant stock changes.

According to the data presented in Figure 4, the immigrant stock was decreasing steadily in Croatia between years 2013 and 2019. The only slight increase was observed in 2020 but it cannot be considered as a trend since 2020 was the year when Covid-19 pandemic began, what highly influenced global migration patterns.

The feminization rate has been dropping steadily since 2013 but it has always remained over 50%.

Figure 4. Foreign-born population, as of 1st January, 2013-2020.

Source: CBS, 2013b.

Figure 5. Age structure of the foreign-born population, as of 1st January, 2013-2020.
Source: Eurostat, 2021a.

Concerning age structure of the foreign-born population, it is observed that the share of persons aged 65 years and more has been increasing over the years, from 22,7% to 28,8%. However, the group consisting of foreign-born residents of Croatia in productive age has always remained the vast majority.

Taking into account the immigrants' citizenship it turns out that a significant part of them had Croatian citizenship (in 2017 that was the case of almost half of all immigrants to Croatia, Eurostat 2019). However, they should not be interpreted altogether directly as return migrants, since many of them have dual citizenships (e.g., immigrants from other Balkan states, in particular in Bosnia and Herzegovina). Thus, many of the immigrants are simply Croats who were born abroad. A lot of them are descendants of Croats who migrated for work during the socialist era (Brzozowski, Banović, Alpeza 2021: 5). Since they come from outside of the EU, they are classified as third country nationals.

Statistical data on immigrant stock available in national databases is incomplete and does not provide information comprehensive enough to analyse migration dynamics in a reliable way. On the other hand, European and other databases present some limited information, allowing to picture major characteristics of immigrant stock in Croatia. Nonetheless, the most recent extensive information including countries of origin or citizenship of immigrants is available only from the Census 2011, making it impossible to characterise immigrant population in a complete way.

5. Immigrant flows in Croatia

The body of statistical data referring to immigrant flows in Croatia is more up-to-date than the one concerning immigrant stocks. It also allows observation of migration processes in a broader time perspective.

Migration flows in Croatia have been changing immensely in the last two decades, from positive net migration at the beginning of the 21st century to negative in recent years.

Figure 6. Immigrants, emigrants and net migration, 2001-2020.

Source: CBS, 2021.

As pictured above (Figure 6), Croatia used to be characterized by positive net migration until 2009 when emigrants outnumbered immigrants. Despite the fact that immigration has been increasing since 2010, net migration remained negative, with the largest gap between the number of immigrants and emigrants in 2017, when the net migration equaled -31 799.

Bosnia and Herzegovina has been by far the main country of origin of immigrants arriving in Croatia, with the largest number of people coming in 2019 (12 040). Until 2018, the second most numerous group of immigrants originated from Germany with a shift in 2019, when persons arriving from Serbia became the second largest immigrant group in Croatia.

Figure 7. Most numerous immigrant groups, 2015-2020.

Source: CBS, 2021.

Table 3. Most numerous immigrant groups, 2015-2020.

Source: CBS, 2021.

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Bosnia and Herzegovina	3804	4348	4949	10348	12040	9438
Germany	1770	2582	2973	3232	3993	3840
Serbia	1038	1368	1272	2880	4800	4704
Slovenia	612	580	622	619	713	1447
North Macedonia	285	213	238	844	1504	1120
Italy	548	627	534	523	592	572

Other relevant countries of origin in the period between 2015 and 2020 were Slovenia, North Macedonia and Italy. The number of people coming from Slovenia increased more than two times between 2019 and 2020, which was one of the largest increases in terms of numbers of immigrants arriving from one country in recent years.

Concerning the sex structure of immigrant flows, Croatian Bureau of Statistics indicates increasing masculinization of immigrant group arriving in all the recent years. The share of men amounted to 55,9% in 2015 (CBS, 2016), 60% in 2016 (CBS, 2017), 63,1% in 2017 (CBS, 2018), 74,6% in 2018 (CBS, 2019), 77,3% in 2019 (CBS, 2020) and 74,6% in 2020 (CBS, 2021a).

Figure 8. Age structure of immigrants arriving in Croatia, 2020.

Source: CBS, 2021a.

Group of young immigrants aged 20-39 years was the largest one in 2020, constituting more than a half (51,4%) of all the people arriving in Croatia in that year. Immigrants aged over 65 years comprised only 5,3% of the whole immigrant flow in 2019 (CBS, 2020) and 5,9% in 2020 which is the opposite to the tendency of increasing share of elderly people in the immigrant stock.

Refugees and asylum seekers

Even though Croatia is European Union's border country, the official statistics considering refugees and asylum seekers are also very restricted. As author of the AIDA report indicates, limited information is available on the Ministry of Interiors website but "a detailed breakdown on all grounds by country of origin in 2020" is not provided (Tučkorić, 2021:7).

Abel and Cohen's estimates

One of our report's aims is to compare Abel and Cohen's estimates of bilateral international migration flows (2019) with statistics collected by national Croatian institutions. Abel and Cohen's estimations are based on the dataset prepared by the United Nations Population Division (UNCPD) referring to the period between 2011 and 2015. According to their calculations, the immigrant flow for Croatia amounted to 159 153 with main groups consisting of Bosnians (115 699), Serbians (14 913), Germans (9 651), Slovenians (5 597) and Macedonians (2 874) (Abel & Cohen, 2019).

Table 4. Comparison of the data on immigration in the period of 2011-2015: CBS, Eurostat and Abel and Cohen's estimations.

Source: Abel and Cohen's, 2019, Eurostat, 2021a; CBS, 2013c.

	Abel & Cohen's estimates	CBS & Eurostat data
Bosnia and Herzegovina	115699	not available
Serbia	14913	not available
Germany	9651	not available
Slovenia	5597	not available
North Macedonia	2874	not available
Total	159 153	-23 854

In the course of our research, we were not able to trace any specific data on countries of origin of immigrants that would allow us to calculate immigrant flows between 2011 and 2015. The only estimation we could have done was the total immigrant flow, based on the information derived both from the Croatian Bureau of Statistics (2013c) and Eurostat (2021a).

According to our calculations, Abel and Cohen's estimates were incorrect and were not able to predict negative net migration in the regarded period of time.

6. Scenario narratives for Croatia

In this subchapter we will focus on the existing migration potential of Croatia as a sending and a host country, considering important push and pull factors: the demographic structure, economic indicators, the social attitudes towards migrants and members of minority groups, the governance and environmental factors. As such, these migration narratives do not aim to foresee the migration future of Croatia, but rather to outline the possible future development of demographic processes in the country, with particular focus on international migration movements.

Migration potential of Croatia

According to recent 2021 census, Croatia has lost almost 400 thousand inhabitants since 2011 (9.25 per cent reduction). The most important factor in this regard was international migration – since EU accession in 2013 over a quarter million of Croatians have left to Western Europe, mostly to Germany, Austria and Ireland. The demographic projections for Croatia are quite pessimistic – according to the UN the current population of 3.89 million could shrink up to 2.5 million by 2100 (Schengenvisainfo, 2022).

Nevertheless, in the recent years we witnessed the stabilization of emigration at ca. 40 thousand persons a year, while in 2020 the migration saldo was lowest in the recent history: 33,414 people immigrated to Croatia, while 34,046 people left the country. Yet, it is definitely too early to say whether the country is starting a migration transition following Polish or Estonian path, especially that year 2020 was peculiar due to covid-19 pandemic. Definitely the migration potential of Croatia will decline in the following years, also as the economic situation of the country should improve, thus limiting some push factors of migration.

Existing migration networks in Croatia

The main migration networks which operate in the country are mostly related to migrant trafficking and smuggling, as Croatia is an important route for irregular migration to Western Europe from South Europe/Balkans (Dumont, 2021). When it comes to existing migration networks for immigrants, the most established group in the country are Bosnians, whose population in Croatia is now estimated at ca. 300 thousand persons. Due to geographical proximity and existing migration networks Croatia already is one of the top destinations for Bosnians: ca. 10 thousand out of 50-55 thousand Bosnians who leave the country every year head to Croatia (Sito-sucic, 2021). As in recent UN survey among young Bosnians 47 per cent of respondents expressed the willingness to emigrate, the role of Bosnian migration networks in Croatia can be substantial and could lead to an increase of migration flows in upcoming years (Sanford, 2021).

Re-emigration policy

The Croatian diaspora is currently estimated at 3 million persons and through its attachment to homeland can be a potential source of re-emigration into the country. The most obvious candidate group is the one in Bosnia and Herzegovina, where the population of ethnic Croatians is estimated at 760 thousand persons. Yet, due to economic hardships at home and still intensive outflow of Croatians to work abroad, reemigration policy is not yet important in political agenda (Winland, 2020).

Receiving refugees

Croatia is not an important destination for refugees, but rather a transit country for asylum-seekers who want to fill application request in Western European countries. The peak in number of applications was in 2016 during the European Migration Crisis (2.15 thousand), and in recent years this number was rising from 880 applications in 2017 to 1540 in 2020 (Eurostat, 2022).

Recruitment agencies

The role of recruiting agencies of immigrants in Croatia is so far not properly addressed in scientific literature and thus is not discussed in this report. During the migration boom in 2000s and 2010s the Croatian specialists, especially from medical professions were recruited by intermediary agencies to Germany and other Western European countries (Wiskow, 2006), but now the role of these actors seems to be diminishing.

Cultural and language proximity

As discussed above, most of immigrants in Croatia come from neighboring countries in Balkans such as Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia, Slovenia and Northern Macedonia. All of these countries were formerly a part of Yugoslavia, therefore cultural and language similarities are substantial in spite of tragic events and military conflicts in 1990s. Moreover, a large group of ethnic Croatians live in Bosnia and Herzegovina and these persons are the most important pool of potential migrants to Croatia in the nearest future.

Picture: Donna Spearman/Unsplash

7. Conclusion

Croatia is traditionally a country of emigration, just like most of CEE and Southern countries. This historical trend has continued till now. Free movement inside the EU granted to Croatia in 2015 led to a major increase in the number of emigrants (migration flow has doubled), mostly in their working-age. A key problem with the official emigration data is their understimation and lack of reliability. When compared to immigration data from destination countries, there are significant discrepancies in statistics related to international mobilities.

In recent period, Croatia has also experienced an influx of immigrants, mostly from less developed countries, such as Bosnia and Herzegovina (who constitute the majority of all foreign-born inhabitants of Croatia) or Serbia. Although immigration is not a completely novel phenomenon for Croatia, as it was observed in the Yugoslavia republic, it has been increasing especially since 2017.

Nevertheless, despite increasing immigration, net migration remains negative. The continuous wave of emigration has changed the whole migration landscape in Croatia and makes the Abel and Cohen's assessments outdated. The Croatian Bureau of Statistics provides incomplete and incomprehensive data about both immigrant stocks and flows, therefore an in-depth analysis is very constricted, even while relying on other databases.

Information about the number of refugees and asylum seekers is also very limited and fragmented, and does not allow conducting appropriate analysis.

According the experts' analyses, official data – both the flow and stocks – are not reflecting the complex migration reality and do not represent the real scale of international migration from and to Croatia.

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